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Fos activation during luminal A subtype specification.

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We studied total transcription in the human breast tumor from humans with luminal A or luminal B subtype cancer to identify genes important for subtype selection during lineage bifurcation. We identified quantitatively significant activation of the AP-1 subunit Fos in the luminal A subtype that appeared biologically relevant for fate choice during lineage bifurcation.